

A Spectrum of Loss: A Socio-Diachronic Analysis of Mortality Perceptions in American Poetry

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To my dad, whose death I will never come to terms with.

Pieter Bruegel the Elder, *Detail from The Triumph of Death*, 1562, oil on panel

Abstract

The learnables of death and loss were analyzed diachronically by examining American poets' perceptions of death in poems across the 19th, 20th, and 21st centuries within the modal of chance and necessity. The analysis emphasized metaphors used to convey

emotions related to death, uncovering their evolution across time. Drawing on thanatology, the study of death and dying in its social and psychological aspects, this article argues that poets' portrayal of death is intrinsically linked to how people live and societal contexts. Medical advancements and science have influenced attitudes toward death, evolving alongside medical inventions. Medical breakthroughs, particularly vaccines and antibiotics, have created new learnables of death through increased life expectancy and decreased mortality. In the 19th and early 20th centuries, disease chances were high; thus, death was often perceived as necessity (i.e., fate and natural). Conversely, during the late 20th and 21st centuries, medical advancements became necessity, lowering death chances. Vaccines have become necessary, reducing illness and death chances. These advancements coincided with a shift from religious society in the 19th century through Darwinian views to a secular society in the 21st century. This added social context to medical advancements, allowing understanding of medical science and cultural contexts while bridging gaps between medical practices and human experiences. By integrating thanatological perspectives, this analysis shows how American poets' depictions of death reflect evolving medical practices, societal values, and human experiences, bridging gaps between medical science, culture, and mortality perceptions.

Keywords: Learnables; Mortality; Socio-Diachronic; Attitude; Poetry.

Perceptions of Death in Poetry Over the Last Three Centuries

The study of death and dying in its social and psychological aspects, or *thanatology*, argues that an individual's experience of death is fundamentally linked to their manner of living (Swensson, 2010, p. 69). This premise, that social context heavily influences mortality perceptions, is reinforced by Moller's (1996, p. 4) contention that "the way one dies is a reflection of the way one lives." Indeed, as the certainty of death is often derived from observing the experiences of others and gathering empirical evidence (Schumacher, 2005, p. 54), an individual's perception of death reflects their core understanding of life. This article explores this fundamental relationship through an analysis of American poetry on death across three centuries. By situating the works of 19th-century poets Emily Dickinson and William Cullen Bryant, 20th-century poets Edna St. Vincent Millay and Robert Frost, and 21st-century poets Karen Chase and Billy Collins within their respective contexts, this exploration reveals a diverse spectrum of emotions and attitudes toward death and loss. Ultimately, poetry

underscores a central theme: the sociocultural context of each era shapes and informs our evolving insights into human mortality.

[*Because I could not stop for Death*](#) is a poem written by Emily Dickinson in the 19th century (Dickinson, 1999, pp. 219-220), revealing her perception of death through metaphors and images.

Because I Could Not Stop for Death

By Emily Dickinson

*Because I could not stop for Death –
He kindly stopped for me –
The Carriage held but just Ourselves –
And Immortality.*

*We slowly drove – He knew no haste
And I had put away
My labor and my leisure too,
For His Civility –*

*We passed the School, where Children strove
At Recess – in the Ring –
We passed the Fields of Gazing Grain –
We passed the Setting Sun –*

*Or rather – He passed Us –
The Dews drew quivering and Chill –
For only Gossamer, my Gown –
My Tippet – only Tulle –*

*We paused before a House that seemed
A Swelling of the Ground –
The Roof was scarcely visible –
The Cornice – in the Ground –*

*Since then – ‘tis Centuries – and yet
Feels shorter than the Day
I first surmised the Horses’ Heads
Were toward Eternity –*

The main metaphor is the carriage ride representing life's journey towards death, with death personified as a courteous guide ("*Because I could not stop for Death – / He kindly stopped for me –*"). Dickinson explores journey stages starting with childhood as she passes a school where children play during recess ("*We passed the School, where Children strove / At Recess – in the Ring –*"), passing grain fields indicating maturity ("*We passed the Fields of Gazing Grain –*"), and finally passing the Setting Sun, representing old age ("*We passed the Setting Sun –*"). The ride ends at a house that looks like A Swelling of the Ground, signifying her grave ("*We paused before a House that seemed / A Swelling of the Ground –*"). Before reaching this house, her journey becomes passive ("*Since then – 'tis Centuries – and yet / Feels shorter than the Day / I first surmised the Horses' Heads / Were toward Eternity –*"). Death determines the journey's end. The transitions are shown through the chill and stillness, her transparent gown, and the netted shawl ("*The Dews drew quivering and Chill – / For only Gossamer, my Gown – / My Tippet – only Tulle –*"). Though death is unpleasant, Dickinson portrays it as a courteous gentleman ("*Because I could not stop for Death – / He kindly stopped for me –*"). Her journey shows calmness and acceptance, presenting death as an inevitable, natural end.

The same perception of death is echoed in [*Thanatopsis*](#), written in the 19th century by William Cullen Bryant (Bryant, 1890, pp. 20-22).

Thanatopsis

By William Cullen Bryant

*To him who in the love of nature holds
Communion with her visible forms, she speaks
A various language; for his gayer hours
She has a voice of gladness, and a smile
And eloquence of beauty, and she glides
Into his darker musings, with a mild
And healing sympathy, that steals away
Their sharpness, ere he is aware. When thoughts
Of the last bitter hour come like a blight
Over thy spirit, and sad images
Of the stern agony, and shroud, and pall,
And breathless darkness, and the narrow house,
Make thee to shudder, and grow sick at heart;—
Go forth, under the open sky, and list
To Nature's teachings, while from all around—*

*Earth and her waters, and the depths of air—
Comes a still voice— Yet a few days, and thee
The all-beholding sun shall see no more
In all his course; nor yet in the cold ground,
Where thy pale form was laid, with many tears,
Nor in the embrace of ocean, shall exist
Thy image. Earth, that nourished thee, shall claim
Thy growth, to be resolved to earth again,
And, lost each human trace, surrendering up
Thine individual being, shalt thou go
To mix forever with the elements,
To be a brother to the insensible rock
And to the sluggish clod, which the rude swain
Turns with his share, and treads upon. The oak
Shall send his roots abroad, and pierce thy mould.
Yet not to thine eternal resting place
Shalt thou retire alone—nor couldst thou wish
Couch more magnificent. Thou shalt lie down
With patriarchs of the infant world—with kings,
The powerful of the earth—the wise, the good,
Fair forms, and hoary seers of ages past,
All in one mighty sepulchre.—The hills
Rock-ribbed and ancient as the sun,—the vales
Stretching in pensive quietness between;
The venerable woods—rivers that move
In majesty, and the complaining brooks
That make the meadows green; and, poured round all,
Old Ocean's gray and melancholy waste,—
Are but the solemn decorations all
Of the great tomb of man. The golden sun,
The planets, all the infinite host of heaven,
Are shining on the sad abodes of death,
Through the still lapse of ages. All that tread
The globe are but a handful to the tribes
That slumber in its bosom.—Take the wings
Of morning—and the Barcan wilderness,
Or lose thyself in the continuous woods
Where rolls the Oregon, and hears no sound,*

Save his own dashings—yet—the dead are there:
And millions in those solitudes, since first
The flight of years began, have laid them down
In their last sleep—the dead reign there alone.
So shalt thou rest—and what if thou withdraw
Unheeded by the living—and no friend
Take note of thy departure? All that breathe
Will share thy destiny. The gay will laugh
When thou art gone, the solemn brood of care
Plod on, and each one as before will chase
His favorite phantom; yet all these shall leave
Their mirth and their employments, and shall come
And make their bed with thee. As the long train
Of ages glide away, the sons of men,
The youth in life's green spring, and he who goes
In the full strength of years, matron and maid,
And the sweet babe, and the gray-headed man—
Shall one by one be gathered to thy side,
By those, who in their turn shall follow them.
So live, that when thy summons comes to join
The innumerable caravan, which moves
To that mysterious realm, where each shall take
His chamber in the silent halls of death,
Thou go not, like the quarry-slave at night,
Scourged to his dungeon, but, sustained and soothed
By an unfaltering trust, approach thy grave,
Like one who wraps the drapery of his couch
About him, and lies down to pleasant dreams.

Thanatopsis presents a serene view on death through nature's metaphor ("To him who in the love of nature holds / Communion with her visible forms, she speaks / A various language;"). Nature, the healer during difficult times, provides comfort by reclaiming the body ("Earth, that nourished thee, shall claim / Thy growth, to be resolved to earth again;"), showing death as a natural, universal phenomenon. This peaceful return to earth evokes serenity, comfort, and unity with nature ("To mix forever with the elements, / to be a brother to the insensible rock / and to the sluggish clod..."). The body then unites with the earth as a sleeping form, completing its cycle. In Bryant's poem, as in Dickinson's, the house symbolizes the grave, humanity's grand tomb surrounded by hills, woods,

and rivers (“...the great tomb of man, The golden sun, / The planets, all the infinite host of heaven, / Are shining on the sad abodes of death, / Through the still lapse of ages.”).

In both poems, the sadness and fear of death depicted through chills and stillness (“*The Dews drew quivering and Chill*” - Dickinson), the last bitter hour (“*The last bitter hour*” - Bryant), and the narrow house (“*We paused before a House that seemed / A Swelling of the Ground*” - Dickinson) are undeniable. However, these emotions are not the main theme, as they are overshadowed by acceptance, serenity, and comfort, shown through the poets’ passive transition from life to death. Metaphors are used to humanize death (“*He kindly stopped for me*” - Dickinson; “*To him who in the love of nature holds / Communion with her visible forms, she speaks / A various language*” - Bryant), transforming negative emotions into positive ones, distracting from the pain of such an experience. Both poets highlight the natural cycle of life and death and peaceful transition to the afterlife, connecting death to a larger force beyond human beings. They achieve this by shifting focus, and our emotions, from fear to acceptance.

Compared to the serene acceptance in the 19th century, the experience of death during the 20th century represents the opposite end of the learnable ¹ spectrum of loss and death, marked by a more intense and resisting attitude. For example, [Edna St. Vincent Millay](#)’s *Dirge Without Music* (Millay, 1928, pp 43-44) and [Robert Frost](#)’s *Out, Out* (Frost, 1924, pp. 50-51)— highlight the container schemas in the poems.

Dirge Without Music

By Edna St. Vincent Millay

*I am not resigned to the shutting away of loving hearts in the hard ground.
So it is, and so it will be, for so it has been, time out of mind:
Into the darkness they go, the wise and the lovely. Crowned
With lilies and with laurel they go; but I am not resigned.*

*Lovers and thinkers, into the earth with you.
Be one with the dull, the indiscriminate dust.
A fragment of what you felt, of what you knew,
A formula, a phrase remains,—but the best is lost.*

*The answers quick and keen, the honest look, laughter, love,—
They are gone. They are gone to feed the roses. Elegant and curled
Is the blossom. Fragrant is the blossom. I know. But I do not approve.*

More precious was the light in your eyes than all roses in the world.

*Down, down, down into the darkness of the grave
Gently they go, the beautiful, the tender, the kind;
Quietly they go, the intelligent, the witty, the brave.
I know. But I do not approve. And I am not resigned.*

‘Out, Out—’

By Robert Frost

*The buzz saw snarled and rattled in the yard
And made dust and dropped stove-length sticks of wood,
Sweet-scented stuff when the breeze drew across it.
And from there those that lifted eyes could count
Five mountain ranges one behind the other
Under the sunset far into Vermont.
And the saw snarled and rattled, snarled and rattled,
As it ran light, or had to bear a load.
And nothing happened: day was all but done.
Call it a day, I wish they might have said
To please the boy by giving him the half hour
That a boy counts so much when saved from work.
His sister stood beside him in her apron
To tell them ‘Supper.’ At the word, the saw,
As if to prove saws knew what supper meant,
Leaped out at the boy’s hand, or seemed to leap—
He must have given the hand. However it was,
Neither refused the meeting. But the hand!
The boy’s first outcry was a rueful laugh,
As he swung toward them holding up the hand
Half in appeal, but half as if to keep
The life from spilling. Then the boy saw all—
Since he was old enough to know, big boy
Doing a man’s work, though a child at heart—
He saw all spoiled. ‘Don’t let him cut my hand off—
The doctor, when he comes. Don’t let him, sister!’
So. But the hand was gone already.
The doctor put him in the dark of ether.
He lay and puffed his lips out with his breath.*

And then—the watcher at his pulse took fright.

No one believed. They listened at his heart.

Little—less—nothing!—and that ended it.

No more to build on there. And they, since they

Were not the one dead, turned to their affairs.

In Millay's poem, "*loving hearts in the hard ground*," "*Into the darkness they go*," and "*down into the darkness of the grave*" represent the container of death, while in Frost's poem, "out" signifies departure from the container of life. Unlike the 19th century perception where death was the natural continuation of life, both poems depict death and life as separate containers occupying different spaces. In *Dirge Without Music*, Millay sets the tone by establishing resistance and refusal, using "without" in the title. This defiance is reiterated with "*I am not resigned*" and "*I do not approve*," urging a fight against death's inevitability ("*I am not resigned to the shutting away of loving hearts in the hard ground*" and "*But I do not approve. And I am not resigned.*"), emphasizing anger, unwillingness, refusal, and sorrow. Millay complicates her resistance by employing the metaphor of life as light, opposing darkness that symbolizes death ("*More precious was the light in your eyes than all the roses in the world*"). The use of flower images ("*With lilies and with laurel they go*," "*They are gone to feed the roses*," and "*is the blossom. Fragrant is the blossom*") contrasts with the grave's reality, emphasizing life's delicacy. These contrasts between light and darkness, delicacy and harshness, highlight the struggle to accept death. Millay acknowledges death's universality: "*So it is, and so it will be, for so it has been, time out of mind.*" She uses 'dust' and 'lost' to express death's harsh reality. Millay mimics death through lexical choices and repetitions in the last stanza. The slow process of death opposes vibrant life: "*Down, down, down into the darkness of the grave*," then "*Gently they go*," followed by "*Quietly they go.*" "*I know. But I do not approve. And I am not resigned.*"

In Robert Frost's *Out, Out*, death is personified as the saw, a modern metaphorical entity. The saw takes on characteristics of a snake, as it "*snarled and rattled in the yard*," intertwining two metaphors—modern machinery and dangerous animal—to convey death's perilous nature, evoke fear, and represent danger. This metaphor encourages resistance or urges individuals to escape, an instinctual survival response. The poet describes the saw ("*The buzz-saw snarled and rattled in the yard*"), symbolizing the industrial age, intensifying fear as it cuts logs into stove-length sticks. The log represents a human being, with the saw (death) taking down individuals, similar to preparing wood for fire. This metaphorical representation intensifies negative

emotions about death, portraying it as relentless, accidental, yet inevitable, claiming lives one by one. The contrast between sweet-scented freshly cut wood, representing life taken away, and the saw's brutal function heightens emotional impact, highlighting the clash between life's beauty and mortality's harsh realities. Though the saw is human-controlled and industrial, it metaphorically "*leaped out at the boy's hand,*" as if possessing its own will ("*As if to prove saws knew what supper meant, / Leaped out at the boy's hand*"). The poet mentions the doctor attempting to save the boy ("*The doctor put him in the dark of ether*"). The saw spilling the boy's life emphasizes the container schema, with life contained within and spilling out. Elements of shock and horror were intensified throughout the narrative.

Edna St. Vincent Millay's *Dirge Without Music* uses darkness to signify death. The clauses "*I am not resigned*" and "*But I do not approve*" are repeated five times, focusing on the refusal and resistance of death. This repetition emphasizes defiance against mortality, drawing the reader into emotional struggle. In Frost's *Out, Out—*, the metaphors of saw with animalistic traits and freshly cut wood represent death and life. This contrast between industrial objects and nature emphasizes the tension between death and life. In contrast, 19th century poems often focus on surroundings and use humanizing metaphors for death. In Emily Dickinson's *Because I could not stop for Death*, death appears as a gentle guide, with the journey to the grave depicted through life stages and peaceful imagery. The word "*death*" appears only in the title, with the poem enveloped in serene narrative. Similarly, in William Cullen Bryant's *Thanatopsis*, the focus is on natural surroundings and life-death cycles. Death is described through metaphors like "*last bitter hour,*" "*narrow house,*" and return to earth, without explicitly mentioning "*dying.*" This shows the shift from death acceptance in the 19th century to direct confrontation in the 20th century. Twentieth century poets like Millay use direct lexical choices to show death's ugly truth, whereas 19th century poets discuss death indirectly within nature and peaceful transition. This reflects the mechanical nature of the 20th century, contrasting with serene 19th-century metaphors.

The depiction of death in 21st century poetry offers a balanced perspective between the extremes of the 19th and 20th centuries. While 19th century poets portrayed death through serene and natural metaphors, emphasizing peaceful transition within life's cycle, 20th century poets highlighted the brutal and mechanical aspects of death, reflecting industrialization's impact. Twenty-first century poetry seeks middle ground (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Learnables of loss and death over the last three centuries

Both Karen Chase's *Before She Died* (Chase, 2000, p. 51) and [Billy Collins](#)' *The Dead*² (Collins, 2002, p. 33) emphasize the enduring bond between the living and deceased, facilitating death's acceptance while resisting complete severance between life and death.

Before She Died

By Karen Chase

*When I look at the sky now, I look at it for you.
As if with enough attention, I could take it in for you.*

*With all the leaves gone almost from
the trees, I did not walk briskly through the field.*

*Late today with my dog Wool, I lay down in the upper field,
he panting and aged, me looking at the blue. Leaning*

*on him, I wondered how finite these lustered days seem
to you. A stand of hemlock across the lake catches*

*my eye. It will take a long time to know how it is
for you. Like a dog's lifetime—long—multiplied by sevens.*

The Dead

By Billy Collins

*The dead are always looking down on us, they say,
While we are putting on our shoes or making a sandwich,
they are looking down through the glass-bottom boats of heaven
as they row themselves slowly through eternity.*

They watch the tops of our heads moving below on earth,

*and when we lie down in a field or on a couch,
drugged perhaps by the hum of a warm afternoon,
they think we are looking back at them,*

*which makes them lift their oars and fall
and wait, like parents, for us to close our eyes.*

Chase attempts to establish a connection between herself and the deceased by connecting with the sky and nature. During fall, as trees lose leaves, the poet walks slowly, marking the process of aging and changes from time's passage ("*With all the leaves gone almost from / the trees, I did not walk briskly through the field*"). This metaphor connecting humans to nature represents death as a natural occurrence of old age. Death is also depicted through the aged dog, who appears "*panting and aged.*" The poet anticipates her dog's loss, reflecting the sorrow she will feel after his death. She understands death's inevitability, but by connecting with the sky while contemplating a loved one's death, she knows they remain connected. This captures the poignant acceptance of mortality and emotional connection that transcends physical presence.

Similarly, in Collins' *The Dead*, the poet establishes an enduring connection with the deceased. Here, the dead look down upon the living from glass boats in heaven ("*The dead are always looking down on us, they say, / while we are putting on our shoes or making a sandwich, / they are looking down through the glass-bottom boats of heaven / as they row themselves slowly through eternity*"). This connection eases death's disconnection, and transparent glass boats create ongoing presence between worlds. When the living gaze at the sky, the dead pause their watchfulness, like parents, until we sleep, emphasizing their protective presence.

Twenty-first century poems are short and simple. This contemporary tendency towards brevity and simplicity mirrors the rapid pace of modern life and need for emotional expressions that align with this lifestyle. This brevity suggests a resolved struggle and lack of conflict. Accepting death while resisting its finality allowed poets to acknowledge death as inevitable yet resist the disconnection causing fear. Thus, they maintain that the dead stay connected to us in various ways. This may reflect the contemporary approach to addressing death's complexities and associated emotions. This creates a balanced view integrating calmness with death's harsh realities.

This middle approach reflects how people resolved the dichotomy between religion and science that existed in the 19th and 20th centuries. Both religion and science, as Hong and Handal (2020, p. 2267) state, offer different ways to reason and reach

conclusions or understand reality. Science is based on data and experiments, whereas religion is based on faith and personal reflections that shape reality using unverified methods of knowing. These epistemological positions can cause confusion, particularly for religious people, who might find it challenging to accept scientific findings without questioning their faith, especially when facts contradict beliefs. Similarly, those who believe in science may struggle to accept religious beliefs lacking empirical evidence. Therefore, in the 19th century, people with strong religious beliefs rejected science, whereas in the 20th century, secularism led people to reject religious faith. In the 21st century, this confusion has been resolved, and the dichotomy between religion and science has been harmonized, finding answers from both realms, as they are not mutually exclusive. This might be due to modern thinking and accepting the coexistence of oppositions, endorsing different perspectives to complement each other and enrich our understanding of reality.

This shift in attitude over time is inevitable and transformative. Swensson (2010, p. 69) stated that perceptions of death and loss shift over time, highlighting that overlooking social progression when considering attitudes is problematic. Davenport (2021, pp. 21-22) explains that developments in social, economic, and technological aspects have led to increased life expectancy and declining mortality rates, improving life expectancy from 30 years in 1800 to 71 years by 2021. This increase demonstrates advancements in public health, sanitation, and medical interventions, leading to a shift in death causes from infectious diseases to non-communicable diseases, including cancer, stroke, and age-related diseases like dementia.

To understand individuals and society's learnables, it is crucial to examine and integrate social, cultural, and political contexts into the analysis. This reveals the factors that have shaped and transformed these learnables, providing a comprehensive understanding of their development. Swensson (2010, p. 70) demonstrated that three historical social shifts influenced attitudes towards death and dying in Europe and America: Protestant reformation, the rise of capitalism in place of feudalism, and industrialization and urbanization. Modern hospitals, medical technologies, and practices have also influenced death. In this article, I extend Swensson's analysis by incorporating a broader historical lens, including epidemiological and religious shifts and contexts. This provides deeper understanding of how learnables result from multifaceted historical, cultural, socioeconomic, and epidemiological influences. When examining the learnables of death, it is essential to consider perceptions of death within health contexts, including life expectancy, mortality rates, prevalent

diseases, available remedies, and socio-religious contexts. Below is a review of the health context of the selected centuries, followed by an examination of the socio-religious contexts of these periods.

Health Context of the Last Three Centuries

Omran's (1971, 1998) epidemiological transition theory describes transformation in three stages. First, *the Age of Pestilence and Famine*, pre-19th to early mid-19th century, characterized by epidemics, infectious diseases, famine, and poor living conditions causing malnutrition, led to fluctuating mortality rates, with life expectancies between 20-40 years. During this age, medicine relied on traditional herbal remedies and primitive surgical practices. Second, *the Age of Receding Pandemics* in the late 19th and early 20th centuries saw declining mortality and fewer epidemics, increasing life expectancy to 50 years. This stage saw improvements in hygiene, public health, and sanitation, with vaccines, antibiotics, and modern health departments emerging. Third, in *the Age of Degenerative and Man-Made Diseases*, starting in the second half of the 20th century, mortality declined, and life expectancy exceeded 50 years, despite increased heart diseases, strokes, cancers, and industrial diseases. This age saw health insurance plans emerge mid-century, with advanced medical solutions and healthcare systems integrating curative and preventive health.

Using the modal of chances and necessity demonstrates that in the 19th and early 20th centuries, disease chances were high due to health conditions, making death a necessity. By contrast, during the late 20th and 21st centuries, medical advancements became necessary, lowering death chances. Vaccines have become necessary, reducing illness chances and mortality rates. Similarly, antibiotics, advanced surgeries, and medical advancements have saved countless lives and lowered death risk. Medical interventions and prevention are necessary in reducing mortality rates. An interesting aspect of the late 20th and 21st centuries is that while causes of death have increased, medical advancements have succeeded in saving countless lives and mitigating death occurrence.

Socio-Religious Context of the Last Three Centuries

19th Century America

These epidemiological ages have been accompanied by transformations due to social, cultural, and scientific shifts. West (2001, p. 182) states that early 19th century America, the Second Great Awakening, witnessed evangelical revivals in both northeast and western regions. This led Evangelical Christians to join the public sphere, forming voluntary associations to preach the gospel and fight poverty, dueling, and alcoholism. This effort reshaped American society's manners and morals, making evangelical Protestantism the dominant religion in American culture. Wilson and Herrnstein (1998, p. 432) note that by 1829, almost 40% of children between ages four and 14 in New York City attended Sunday schools. By 1860, almost 50% of Protestant males in New York City belonged to at least one voluntary association affiliated with a church.

Regarding medicine in the early 19th century, the “pastor-physician” phenomenon declined significantly. Imber (2008, p. 71) argues that medicine lacked intellectual credibility to separate from organized religion; physicians embraced religion, presented medical reasons to avoid sins, and considered their profession sacred. European Americans continue to pray to stay healthy and recover when sick (Waller, 2014, p. 52). According to Waller (2014, p. 51), during this century, people of European, African, and Native descent attributed illness to breaking religious taboos. Nevertheless, they believe God created plants and minerals to medicate sick people and established supernatural healing rituals.

In 1832, cholera's arrival in the United States, as Waller (2014, p. 53) states, highlighted how religion influences views on diseases. The death of thousands from cholera was attributed to God's disapproval of sinners, as this disease hit hardest in “the squalor and vice of city slums.” Rosenberg (1987, p. 4), New York City's governor, argued:

an infinitely wise and just God had seen fit to employ pestilence as one means of scourging the human race for their sins, and it seems to be an appropriate one for the sins of uncleanness and intemperance.

A New York pastor claimed this is God's way to “drain off the filth and scum which contaminate and defile human society” (p. 96). During cholera epidemics of 1832, 1849, and 1866, sin and immorality were believed to have played a role in the spread of the disease (Waller, 2014, p. 53). Therefore, they advocated improving morality to combat the pandemic.

Medical reasons that represented immorality as the disease's cause and showed a lack of empathy for those in poverty and poor sanitation were unproductive. As Waller (2014, p. 54) argued, improving morality failed to address the lack of sanitary conditions in American cities. Seeking divine interventions through fasting and prayers, such as those ordered by Pennsylvania's governor in 1832 and President Taylor's White House in 1849 to combat the epidemic, did not work. Such religious justification allowed wealthy landlords, who built squalid dwellings for the poor, to shift blame and avoid improving sanitation in the slums (Brieger, 1985, pp. 185-196). Nevertheless, the higher social classes, particularly Christian gentlemen driven by duty to provide for the needy, attempted to alleviate suffering by providing food, clothes, and disinfectants to slum dwellers. Consequently, they succeeded in combatting the pandemic (p. 193).

Physicians called for improving slum and city living conditions as a religious duty, establishing a Bath and Wash House in 1852, and passing laws regulating milk quality (Rosenberg, 1968, pp. 16-35). Physicians and people favored practical solutions, such as building sewers and laying water pipes, over religious solutions like fasting and praying. This created a drift between physicians and clergymen, who once celebrated their union, with growing fear of religion losing relevance. Imber (2008, p. 71) states that in 1866, Reverend Abram Newkirk Littlejohn advised physicians to perceive the human body purely as "nucleated cells," highlighting the growing gap between theology and medicine. This marked "the decline in the cultural authority of religion as Americans became more secular in outlook" (Waller, 2014, p. 57). By 1878, 50 American cities established health departments, including boards of health, in 16 states (Waller, 2014, p. 128). More sanitation initiatives driven by germ theory were carried out to combat widespread infectious diseases. By 1894, vaccines in New York had been offered to the public.

Due to sanitation initiatives, increasing access to filtered water, public health, milk laws, vaccines, and other developments in city life, life expectancy significantly increased in early 1900s America (Waller, 2014, p. 132). Yoo (2021) argued that in the late 19th century, higher education saw a harmonious relationship between Christianity and science, with science providing evidence for God's existence. Conflicts, including those with Darwinism, were viewed as opportunities for reconciliation. However, intellectual debates, American pragmatism, and German liberalism in the early 20th century caused a division between science and religion in American higher education. They separated religion from natural sciences, moving it

to philosophy, ethics, and religious studies or social sciences, allowing them to strengthen their position independently. This has led theologians to view science as a threat to their religious and biblical knowledge. The evidentialist approach diminished religion's status as a science, relegating it to personal experiences, religious practices, and social transformation. This marked the beginning of science and American higher education's secularization, while elevating faith to a sacrosanct, non-scientific field of study (Williams, 2019). The term 'secular' was first coined in the mid-19th century (Cragun & Manning, 2017, p. 4).

By the end of the 19th century, white physicians practicing European medical traditions became more critical of mixing religious beliefs with medical practices. As they learned about new discoveries in body functions, they sought to establish a professional identity separate from the church. Therefore, they treat diseases without referring to God. This marked a shift in medical and religious practices. Nevertheless, new quasi-medical sects, such as Christian Science, became popular across America, attracting those who believed in medical practices inspired by theological views on healing. Religion continued to influence the medical practices of many white, black, and indigenous healers by the end of the 19th century. As Dye and Smith (1986, p. 335) note, death during the 19th century was viewed as divine will. This explains why death was perceived as natural, inevitable, and integral to life, demonstrating the acceptance of mortality as an unavoidable facet of human existence.

20th Century America

Butler (2003) states that 19th century American religious leaders doubted religion would survive the next century due to urbanization, industrialization, bureaucratization, and modern technological and scientific transformation. Although traditional organized religion declined in the 20th century, it did not die out. Instead, it adapted and persisted in different forms, continuing to influence American culture and society. The dominance of Protestants in America during the 19th century faded, making room for Catholics and Jews. Due to postwar conditions and religious diversity, in the 1930s, religious leaders began using "the Judeo-Christian tradition" to address America's growing pluralism. This phrase included Jews, Protestants, and Catholics, highlighting a non-existent consensus between these groups but excluding others, including Mormons, Jehovah's Witnesses, and Buddhists (Balmer, 2001, pp.44-45). Since 1965, mainline churches and their denominations have been losing members, even as the American population increases. Between the 1930s and 1960s, "Americans

were growing increasingly confused and uneasy about the varieties of religion around them” (p. 43). This confusion was echoed by President Dwight Eisenhower, who stated in 1952 that “our form of government makes no sense unless it is founded in a deeply felt religious faith, and I do not care what it is” (Espinosa, 2009).

Butler and Stout (2001, p. 7) stated that in the 20th century, the Death of God was proclaimed, as “the forces of modernization would inevitably secularize Western society and render religious belief old-fashioned.” Rupke (2009, p. 31) argues that 20th century science was viewed as a secular religion. The debate on science’s role in secularizing society remains controversial, with historian John Hedley Brooke arguing that this view oversimplifies the relationship between science, religion, and society, as other factors contribute (Numbers, 2009, p. 351). Sundberg (2000, p. 23) states that church officials explained this trend as modern secularization in “post-Christian” America, where organized religion ceased attracting people and left the public sphere. Campbell and Layman (2017, p. 3) note that the 20th century saw fluctuations. Religion was strong in 1950s America, declined in the 1960s due to counter-cultural shock, then rebounded in the 1970s due to social changes, particularly sexual liberalization. As religious generations died, younger, less religious Americans emerged (p. 3). Both Chaves (1994) and Gorski (2000) indicated that incompatibility between scientific and religious authority weakened religious authority’s relevance.

21st Century America

Scott (2017, p. 1) states that the early 21st century, after September 11th attacks, marked a shift, as anti-religious arguments reached the mainstream in America, justified invading Iraq and Afghanistan, and proliferated through best sellers like the ‘New Atheists’ such as *The End of Faith* (Harris 2005), *The God Delusion* (Dawkins 2006), and *God is not Great* (Hitchens 2009). Baker and Smith (2009) demonstrated that religiosity is gendered, as women are usually more religious than men due to social and psychological factors. Gallup (2013) showed that in 1973, 43% of Americans had a “great deal” of confidence in “the church or organized religion,” whereas only 25% did in 2012. The percentage of Americans who do not attend religious services nearly doubled from 13% in the 1990s to 22% in 2008 (Chaves, 2011). Since 2000, Americans unaffiliated with any religion has increased (Putnam & Campbell, 2010; Pew, 2012). The number of unaffiliated Americans grew from 36 million in 2007 to 47 million in 2012 (Pew 2012). Lipka (2015) states that “religious nones,” usually the millennial generation, refers to atheists, agnostics, or those unaffiliated with any religion, and

their percentage is increasing. Gallup Polls showed that 1% of Americans did not believe in God in 1967 whereas 7% did not in 2011 (Crabtree, 2011). Secularism emerged from modernization, leading to secular ideas and practices. As Bonhoeffer argues,

[t]he rise of modernism led to the rise of secularism. The two go hand-in-hand. Secularism is defined as a system of ideas or practices that reject the primacy of religion in our corporate life” (as cited in Popovska et al., 2009, p. 35).

It can also be viewed as a political effort to reduce religious establishments’ influence on public life. Smith (2003, p. 1) argued that American public life’s secularization resulted from activists’ deliberate political attempt to “overthrow a religious establishment’s control over socially legitimate knowledge” between 1930-1970, not from modernization. While modernization fostered secularism, political actions also contributed to its advancement. As Joseph Bottum suggests in *An Anxious Age* (Bottum, 2014), religion influences American society in new forms. While traditional religious adherence declined, spiritual sentiments persist, allowing 21st century poets to maintain connections with the deceased through spiritual personal experience.

Mapping Learnables of Death Over the Last Three Centuries

To map these centuries, creating an integrated framework offers comprehensive context for the three historical periods. This approach facilitates understanding of death’s learnables influenced by shifts in belief systems and advancements in medical knowledge and public health practices. By aligning relevant contexts, I demonstrate how health factors like life expectancy, mortality rates, diseases, and remedies, along with religious beliefs, provide insights into practical medical realities across periods. This framework shows how religious contexts, influenced by medical advancements, shape attitudes towards death (Fig. 2). Considering health and religious perspectives, the interplay between empirical and experiential dimensions reveals a comprehensive picture of historical and contemporary learnables surrounding death.

Age of Pestilence and Famine (Pre-19th Century to Early-Mid 19th Century)	Age of Receding Pandemics (Late 19th Century to Early 20th Century)	Age of Degenerative and Man-Made Diseases (Mid-20th Century to 21st Century)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Belief System: Predominantly religious society. • Health Indicators: Characterized by high mortality rates and low life expectancy (20-30+ years). • Causes of Death: Major causes included infectious diseases, malnutrition, disasters, and wars. • Pandemic: Smallpox Epidemics: Various outbreaks from 1751 to 1782; Yellow Fever Epidemic in Philadelphia: 1793; Cholera Pandemics: 1832-1833, 1849-1850, 1866; Yellow Fever Epidemics: 1793, 1878 • Characteristics: Poor sanitation, low standards of living, and unsanitary environments were common. • Health System: Relied on herbal remedies, barber surgery, cautery, bloodletting, bone setting, sometimes witchcraft, chiropractic, and Christian Science. Physicians used mustard plasters and arsenic, mercury, and other poisons for infectious diseases. • Perception: Death was viewed as a natural part of life, often accepted as inevitable due to the harsh living conditions and lack of medical knowledge. This acceptance aligns with the religious beliefs being backgrounded, where death perception is shaped by spiritual beliefs rather than personal emotional. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Belief System: Transitioned from religious flux to a more secular society with the onset of modernity. • Health Indicators: Decreased mortality rates and increased life expectancy (40-50 years). • Causes of Death: Included several communicable diseases, heart diseases, strokes, and cancer. • Pandemic: The 1918 Influenza Pandemic • Characteristics: Marked by the beginnings of sanitation and public health improvements, better housing, and the development of tenements which led to modest improvements in living conditions. • Health System: Introduction of vaccines, antibiotics, successful organ transplant, and medical technology. • Changes: Establishment of health departments. • Perception: Death began to be seen as a failure, particularly in the context of preventable diseases. This led to resistance against death, reflecting the failure of medical advancement to save lives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Belief System: Post-secularism and beyond modernity. • Health Indicators: High life expectancy and low mortality rates (50-75 years). • Causes of Death: Primarily heart diseases, strokes, cancer, diabetes, pulmonary diseases, metabolic disorders, environmental pollutants, motor vehicle and aviation accidents, and exposure to carcinogens in industry, environment, or food additives. • Pandemic: The 2020 COVID-19 Panedmic • Characteristics: Significant and gradual improvement in living conditions and sanitation. • Health System: Advanced medical solutions with modern healthcare systems that integrated curative and preventive health measures. • Changes: Introduction and widespread use of health and life insurance plans in the mid-20th century. • Perception: Death is increasingly seen as a personal experience, thus they accept death as part of life but they resist death and mortality by establishing an enduring connection with the dead.

Figure 2. Historical Mapping of Death Learnables Across Three Centuries

During *the Age of Pestilence and Famine*, spanning the pre-19th century to early-mid 19th century, society was predominantly religious, with spirituality intertwined with daily life. Religious institutions played a central role in explaining and coping with illness and death. Health indicators showed high mortality rates and low life expectancy, typically 20 to 30+ years. Given this brief life expectancy, households were limited to two generations and deaths were frequent. Grandchildren rarely knew their grandparents. Major causes of death included infectious diseases like plague and smallpox, malnutrition, natural disasters, and wars, worsened by poor living conditions. For infectious diseases, “physicians continued to attack the body with mustard plasters that blistered the body, along with arsenic, mercury, and other poisons.” (Barry, 2004, p. 30). Significant pandemics included smallpox outbreaks from 1751 to 1782, the 1793 Yellow Fever Epidemic in Philadelphia, and multiple cholera pandemics (1832-1833, 1849-1850, 1866). This era was marked by poor sanitation, low living standards, and unsanitary environments, facilitating disease spread. Medical practices were rudimentary, relying on herbal remedies, barber surgery, cautery, bloodletting, bone-setting, and witchcraft. Due to harsh conditions, infectious diseases, and limited medical knowledge reinforced by fatalistic attitudes, death was viewed as natural and inevitable. In the late 19th century, “America continued to churn

out prophets of new, simple, complete, and self-contained systems of healing, two of which, chiropractic and Christian Science, survive today' (Barry, 2004, p. 31).

Religious beliefs in the divine and frequent occurrences of death implicitly shape the learnables of death, loss, and influence behavior. For believers who see death as part of a divine plan, this backgrounded experience is perceived as a property of the external world. Core affect is characterized by peace, acceptance, and readiness derived from faith in God and belief in the afterlife. Their attitude towards death is not viewed merely as a personal reaction but as part of their response to religious beliefs. Their religious beliefs shaped their emotional experiences of death, along with their core affect and attitude. Limited medical understanding and primitive healthcare systems meant death was often seen as inevitable and beyond control. This lack of agency reinforced the background of core affect, with death influencing consciousness implicitly. Since backgrounded beliefs and frequent occurrences of death were aligned, death was both expected and accepted. The predominantly religious society of the 19th century viewed death as part of a divine plan, leading to passive acceptance of death as natural.

The Age of Receding Pandemics, from the late 19th to early 20th century, saw a transition from religious to secular society with modernity. Religion's influence waned as scientific understanding grew. Health indicators showed decreased mortality and increased life expectancy to 40-50 years. This rise in life expectancy contributed to multigenerational households in America, where grandparents, parents, and grandchildren live together. Causes of death included communicable diseases, heart disease, stroke, and cancer. The 1918 Influenza Pandemic marked this era significantly. While infectious diseases remained prevalent, public health measures began mitigating their impacts. This period saw sanitation and public health improvements. Better housing and tenements improved living conditions. Vaccines, antibiotics, and medical technology improved health outcomes, while health departments formalized public health efforts.

Advancements in medical technology, particularly vaccines and antibiotics, have led people to develop negative attitudes towards death, questioning faith, losing trust in religious beliefs, and placing more trust in the medical community. Advances in medical technology have extended life expectancy and improved quality of life, leading to greater trust in medicine. Advances in medical science made death seem more preventable. This shift made death more difficult to reconcile with, as it was

increasingly seen as a failure of medical intervention rather than a natural part of life, causing uncertainty regarding attitudes towards death and science. When expectations are unmet and death occurs, emotional responses are immediately felt. Rejection and negative reactions to death might be a response to the limitations of science experienced through death. This interplay highlights how medical progress can influence perceptions of mortality and societal trust. Death began to be seen as a failure, particularly with preventable diseases, as medical advances created the expectation of curing diseases. In 20th century poems, death was often resisted and difficult to accept. As societies became more secular, rejection of death grew, with less reliance on religious explanations causing stronger emotional reactions. Since their beliefs in science and less frequent death were aligned, death was not only rejected but seen as a failure of trust in science. This perception stems from expecting scientific advancements to save lives. When science failed to save lives, it was perceived as failure, leading to reshaping of their understanding of loss and death compared to the 19th century.

The Age of Degenerative and Man-Made Diseases, from the mid-20th to 21st century, is characterized by post-secularism, moving beyond traditional religious beliefs toward a more diverse spiritual landscape. Health indicators show high life expectancy and low mortality rates, typically 50 to 75 years. This improved life expectancy has decreased death frequency within families. The primary causes of death have shifted to degenerative and man-made diseases like heart disease, stroke, cancer, diabetes, pulmonary diseases, and metabolic disorders. Environmental pollutants, motor vehicles, aviation accidents, and carcinogen exposure are significant causes of death. Improvements in living conditions and sanitation contributed to better public health. Advanced medical solutions, including health care systems integrating curative and preventive measures, have become standard. The introduction of health and life insurance plans in the mid-20th century supported this system. Death is increasingly viewed as a personal experience influenced by individual health choices and medical interventions. Despite medical advancements, death remains inevitable, with greater emphasis on personal reflection and emotional processing. Personal responsibility and medical progress shape attitudes towards health and death, leading people to accept them as part of life. However, they resist death by fostering connections with the deceased, as shown in the selected poems. By maintaining these bonds, individuals create continuity and comfort, helping them navigate grief and maintain the presence of loved ones. This balance between acceptance and resistance highlights the need to find meaning in mortality.

Balancing resistance and acceptance are influenced by increased life expectancy and decreased mortality rates, which allows death to be viewed as an expected end after a long life. This acceptance is shown in end-of-life care, such as hospice care, and death as a choice, such as in decisions to terminate a pregnancy or remove life support when recovery seems impossible. It introduces the notion of merciful death. The rise of life insurance has fostered the idea that life can be compensated with money, making death profitable. According to Zelizer (1978, p. 591), in the 19th century, the monetary value of life through life insurance was rejected and considered a profit, making death a commodity instead of a sacred event. By the latter part of the same century, life insurance had become more acceptable, desacralizing death. By the 21st century, “life insurance has become more prevalent. . .as employers seek to manage costs and as the nature of work changes” (Kuehner-Hebert, 2017) and have become an increasingly important part of the financial sector over the past 40 years, providing a range of financial services for consumers and becoming a major source of investment in the capital market’ (Beck & Webb, 2003, p. 51). This interplay between medical advancements, societal attitudes, and economic factors shows how perceptions of death and life evolve over time. Hence, one’s learnables change, particularly those relevant to the emotions and attitudes associated with death.

Epidemiological ages form the central framework, underscoring Moller’s (1996, p. 4) argument that “the way one dies is a reflection of the way one lives.” This emphasizes that perception of death is fundamentally associated with understanding and experiences of life. Capturing the evolving epidemiological landscape is necessary to understand shifts in sociocultural and religious landscapes, highlighting the interplay between health, culture, and religion. Health systems are often overlooked as indicators driving changes in society at cultural and religious levels, and vice versa. This mutual influence shapes perception of life and death and can influence decisions, social behavior, and worldview. Through mechanisms of backgrounding and foregrounding, emotions towards death are managed by learnables. More studies are needed to understand how medical communities and practices can drive change and influence societal shifts and emotions associated with life and death. This research is crucial for highlighting relationships between health, culture, and beliefs. By examining these connections, we can gain understanding of human experience, especially in response to health events such as pandemics, to inform better practices.

Conclusion

This article shows that death and loss learnables over three centuries in American poems are deeply rooted in poets' attitudes and their representation of death, along with emotions associated with death within social contexts. Attitudes toward death have evolved alongside medical inventions. In the 19th and early 20th centuries, disease rates were high; thus, death was often perceived as necessity (i.e., fate and natural). By contrast, during the late 20th and 21st centuries, medical advancements became necessary; therefore, death rates are lower. In this sense, vaccines have become necessary, reducing illness and death chances. Medical breakthroughs, particularly vaccines and antibiotics, which increased life expectancy and decreased mortality rates, have influenced the learnables of death. These advancements led to a shift from a religious society in the 19th century through Darwinian evolutionary views in the late 19th and early 20th centuries to a secular society in the 21st century. This added a social aspect to medical advancements, enabling understanding of medical science and social contexts while bridging gaps between medical practices, science, and human experiences. By integrating thanatological perspectives, this analysis shows how American poets' depictions of death reflect evolving medical practices, societal values, and human experiences, bridging gaps between medical science, culture, and mortality perceptions. This study had limitations. The analysis was limited to six poems, two from each century, as poets reflect on their society. Although these poems represent how poets negotiated death learnables of their time and the mapping of three centuries' contexts offered a foundation for analysis, they cannot be used to generalize these learnables. Further studies are needed to better understand the evolution of death perceptions and learnables across different periods and cultural contexts.

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- 1 On the concept of the “learnable”, see Magni et al. (2023) and Magni et al. (2024). The Learnable is the cognitive horizon—made by shared socio-cognitive schemata, set interactively by a community, and reciprocally recognized and interiorized by its members—that limit individuals’ access to reality.
- 2 *The Dead* was first published in 1991 in the collection *Questions about Angels*, making it a transition piece from the 20th to the 21st century.

A guest post by

Ahlam Alharbi

I am a discourse analyst. I am interested in the applications of critical discourse analysis in social studies to understand how language constructs and reflects power dynamics, ideology, and social phenomena.